

Nonlinear Integral-Type Sliding Surface for Synchronization of Chaotic Systems with Unknown Parameters

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Abstract : This paper presents a new nonlinear integral-type sliding surface for synchronizing two different chaotic systems with parametric uncertainty. On the basis of Lyapunov theorem and average dwelling time method, we obtain the control gains of controllers which are derived to achieve chaos synchronization. In order to reduce the gains, the error system is modeled as a switching system. We obtain the sufficient condition drawn for the robust stability of the error dynamics by stability analysis. Then we apply it to guide the design of the controllers. Finally, numerical examples are used to show the robustness and effectiveness of the proposed control strategy.

Keywords : Chaos synchronization, Nonlinear sliding surface, Control gains, Sliding mode control.

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